

Transition to Post-pandemic Education in the Philippines: Concerns of Elementary Teachers

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Abstract. This study examined the experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational insights of Senior High School teachers in the Babak District, Division of IGACOS, Philippines, in fostering resilience among English learners. Using a qualitative-phenomenological approach, the study explored the challenges teachers encountered as they navigated the shift back to face-to-face learning post-pandemic. Data collected through in-depth interviews revealed three major themes in teachers' experiences: managing workload stress through hybrid education models, addressing learning loss, and dealing with inequities among students. Teachers also employed several coping strategies, including building strong support networks, staying flexible with instructional approaches, and prioritizing student well-being. Insights for educational management highlighted the importance of equity and inclusion, underscoring the need for resource allocation and targeted interventions. Findings suggest that supporting teachers with professional development and psychological resources can enhance resilience, ultimately benefiting students' learning outcomes. This study contributes valuable insights for policymakers aiming to support educators in post-pandemic educational transitions.

KEY WORDS

1. Post Pandemic Education
2. Elementary Concerns
3. Learning Loss
4. Professional Development

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1. Introduction

Since the rise and threat of the pandemic, many countries around the world have decided to temporarily close schools that have affected millions of students. Consequently, students who are mostly children have been facing a learning crisis due to the pandemic. Despite the threat of the pandemic, the need to ensure learning continuity for children around the globe drove schools to slowly reopen its doors to the learners. School reopening for face-to-face interactions must be carefully planned to ensure the safety of students as well as teach-

ers and school staff in a staged fashion especially in following physical distancing. Planning and execution of school health protocols during this pandemic must be supported by the truthful data being given by various institutions. School health protocols in conducting face to face classes must be planned carefully following national and international guidelines to ensure that students will be safe or at least mitigate the effects of COVID-19. After all, students' lives matter as education does to them. That is the responsibility of every government to en-

sure its fulfillment. Globally, it's a given knowledge that every country has the responsibility to come up with strategies to reopen schools in a safe manner. Last December 2020, the World Health Organization (2020) published a checklist to support school reopening and the preparation for the possible resurgence of COVID-19. WHO cited that the checklist is aligned with, and builds upon, existing COVID-19-related WHO guidelines and is structured around protective measures. While every nation had its own specific policies in place, the guideline released by WHO helps policymakers and school officials from different regions of the world to enhance compliance and adherence to public health protocols in the time of the pandemic. In the USA, the steps taken include prioritizing vaccine access for school staff, expanding access for young people, and performing testing and contact tracing, and universal indoor masking. In Indonesia, schools returned to in-person learning at 50% in the national setting, the Philippine Department of Education has come up with guidelines to implement online and modular distance learning delivery of instruction. This is to safeguard students from being infected by the disease. However, plans to conduct the pilot implementation of limited face-to-face delivery

in low-risk areas of COVID-19 transmission for January 2021 have been approved by the president but was later recalled due to the threat of the new strain of COVID-19. Predicaments are raised whether the country is ready to open its schools for students to go for face-to-face learning despite having been one of the longest and strictest lockdowns in the world. A year later, on August 2022, and among the last few nations to do so, public and private schools across the nation have finally reopened its doors to some 28 million Filipino students. In the lead-up to the reopening of classrooms, the government has been ramping up a vaccination drive that aimed to provide students with free public transport until the end of the calendar year. In the local scenario particularly in Talomo, Davao City, statewide and schoolwide policies and guidelines have also been implemented as students were welcomed back to school. The transition back to face-to-face classes from the years long implementation of blended/online learning has caused serious whiplash to teachers and students alike. I discerned there is a need to take a deeper look into the post pandemic education status of Philippines schools and to identify the main challenges and coping mechanisms of teachers as they go through the transition.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study provided insight into the transition to post pandemic education in the Philippines and the experiences of teachers on the return of students to school. The coping strategies along with the challenges faced by the teachers was identified by the end of this study. With these, the teachers gave insights based on their personal experience.

1.2. Research Questions—

- (1) What are the challenges encountered by teachers during the transition to post pandemic education?
- (2) How do teachers cope with the challenges?
- (3) What educational insights can be drawn from the post pandemic education experiences of teachers?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Post pandemic education. an organized effort to reinvent education

to return to the status quo, a focus on remediating learning loss and returning to face to face instruction following state and institution-specific health protocols.

1.4. Significant of the Study—To clearly determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. Department of Education Personnel. The DepEd, particularly the District of Talomo, Davao City, to identify challenges that burden the teachers during the transition to post pandemic education and to show better support to the educators. The School Principals and Head teachers. For the school principals and school heads to gain a clear thought on the the impact of post pandemic education to teachers and how they can

be provided with better support. The Teachers. The findings of this study shall benefit the teachers as the participants of this study unravels their thoughts and personal experiences during the delivery of their respective work during post pandemic education. The Future Researchers. For the future researchers to take into consideration some other aspects of teachers' challenges and coping mechanisms throughout the transition and to gain other information that may be useful in furthering this study. Other areas pertaining to this study may be conducted in other grade levels and districts.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored on the Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory. Hannah and Topping (2013) used this theory to design their transition programme which they evaluated, rather than using it for research. As mentioned earlier, Brewin and Statham (2011) organised their findings around the ecosystems; they reported that it was a useful way of showing the factors, and their interaction, that had an impact on looked after teachers' and children's transitions. Waters et al. (2014a) used the theory to explain the role of contexts in human development, with school being such a context; whereas in (Waters et al., 2014b) they use the Ecological Systems Theory to conceptualise the support systems of young people as they move to secondary school. Similarly, Strnadova and Cumming (2014), Strnadova et al. (2016), and Booth and Sheehan (2008) used the theory to understand transitions and relationships in the ecosystems of young

people moving to secondary school. Four of the papers had a negative discourse, one both (Hannah and Topping, 2013) and one neutral (Strnadova and Cumming, 2014). It is interesting to note that although Booth and Sheehan (2008), and Strnadova and Cumming used the same theory, they used different discourses about transition. Another theory that has some relevance is Stage-Environment Fit Theory. It focuses primarily on students rather than to educators. This theory emphasises the mismatch between the adolescent's developmental stage and associated needs, compared to the demands of the secondary school environment (Benner and Graham, 2009). Although the theory was created to explain psychological development across the middle school transition, it does not explain school transition as a process per say. Rather it can be used to refer to any systemic change in environment and how this connects to change in a person's psychology, depending on the person's stage of development.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the research design that was used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection, the data analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical consideration. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviours in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals’ personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, “What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people? Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. A good research – undertaking with the selection of the topic, problem or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces ‘paradigm ‘ back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an action of submitting to a view. This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000) who defend a research paradigms a “basic set of belief that guide action”, dealing with first principles, “ultimates’ or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012) reality is a subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realist exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals

being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of the teachers related to their resiliency throughout the global pandemic were drawn out. In this study, I relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidences of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure reliability of result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precludes from making personal bias as the study progress. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible as during the study in order obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985) as cited by Creswell (2013) state that on epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an “insider.” Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). I will identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief”. The intention of this research is to put together the details about the experiences of the teachers in their transition to post pandemic education in the District of Talomo, Davao City. I assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that will shed light to the knowledge behind the inquiry particularly on the experiences and coping mechanisms of the

teachers during the global pandemic in their respective classes. . Axiology refers to role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes own interpretation in conjunction with interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. I therefore preserve the merit of the participant’s answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant’s personal interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and uses qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in explaining the transition to post pandemic education. As a researcher, I agree with the post modernism philosophy of Afzal-os-sadat Hossieni (2011). I believe that the aims of education are teaching critical thinking, production of knowledge, development of individual and social identity, self-creation. In postmodern education teachers just lead students to discover new things. They provide opportunities to discuss about different subjects and make creative ways. In this situation student learn to listen to other voices. They tolerate others criticism and try to think in critical way. They learn to respect other cultures and nationalities. Also they emphasize on cooperative learning independent learning, and dialectic, critical and verbal methods. It is deducted that postmodernism and creativity are embedded in each other and we can find the result of this opinion in postmodern education.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology is different from method. Methodology

is creative and responsive approach to understand questions and subject matter while method

refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the transition to post pandemic education was dug deeper, especially for the teachers of Talomo District, Davao City. The researcher's interest on the transition to post pandemic education became the basis for doing a qualitative research, a means of which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and phenomena". By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols and meaning of the experiences will be presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994). The data was then read and reread and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this pro-

2.4. Research Participants—The participants in this study were composed of eight (8) informants. The selected informants were the elementary teachers coming from Talomo District, Davao City. All the teacher participants were coming from the elementary who handled classes last school year 2021-2022. The participants must have at least 3 years' experience in teaching. The participants were further selected regardless of their age, sex and marital

According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology which concerns with that "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher hoped that the personal experiences and perspectives of the teachers in how they remained resilient during a pandemic, their coping mechanisms and insights were determined and examined.

cess the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation or experiences and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. In this study phenomenology attempts to extract the most pure, untainted data and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing is used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is memoing (Maxwell, 2013).

status. Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size the quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions will lead to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving

an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25 and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample

size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Informed Consent and Voluntary Participation The participants were adequately informed about the research undertaking through an informed consent. Consent was given freely and the researcher made sure that the participants understood what was being asked and emphasized that their participations were just purely voluntary. All participants were required to provide written informed consent. The potential participants were approached individually online and given an explanation of the purpose of the study and data collection process. They were also given an appropriate time to ask questions and address concerns. It was explained that their participation was voluntary; they may also refuse to participate or withdraw from the study while it was in progress. When the participants agreed to be part of the In-Depth Interview (IDI), a date, time, and venue were set.

and confidentiality of the interview environment were managed carefully during the interview sessions, data analysis and dissemination of the findings. The confidentiality of handling the data is in accordance to Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Interview Sessions Each interview was conducted individual through online. The interview was done with the use of google meet, google sheets and messenger application. The researcher was the only knowledgeable person who can match the identity of the participants in voice and in video recordings. In recording the data, interviews were audio-taped and video recorded with the permission of the participants, and the voice records were transcribed verbatimly. Some notes were taken by the researcher to have genuine, accurate and authentic transcription but the identification of the information of the participants were removed or disguised. Further, the interviews, transcriptions and consent forms were kept in a secured location. To safeguard confidentiality, consent forms were stored in a separate location from the other data so there is no way they can be linked to the interviews.

Anonymity and Confidentiality The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were preserved by not revealing their names and identity in the data collection, analysis and reporting of the study findings. Privacy

*2.6. Role of the Researcher—*The role of the researcher in this study was to attempt to access the thoughts and feelings of study participants. It involves asking informants to talk about things that may be very personal to them. Sometimes the experiences being explored are fresh in the participant's mind, whereas on other

occasions reliving past experiences may be difficult. However the data are being collected, a primary responsibility of the researcher is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins.

2.7. Data Collection—

According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process is to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they will provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data such as interview or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called “field issues,” which may be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, there are seven steps in the process of data collection. First is the site or individual; the participants were the elementary teachers from Talomo District, Davao City. Second is the access and rapport; letter from the Dean of the Graduate School is given to the graduate student for the approval of the division superintendent; letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal and the concerned elementary teachers were prepared for easy collection of data. The third is the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants have experienced the phenomenon being studied. There were eight (8) informants selected in this study. The qualified elementary teachers were considered group of individuals who can best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered as individuals who have

experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the collection of data. The fourth is the forms of data; the process of collecting information involved primarily in the Virtual In-Depth Interview (IDI) with the eight (8) informants. The fifth is the recording procedures; the use of a protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form used to record information collected during an observation or interview. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or the seventh step was the storing of data; Davidson’s (1996) suggested the use of database in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies.

The COVID 19 Health Protocols. The data was collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time, therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (AITF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippines which was convened in January 2020. The Collection of data or the Virtual In Depth Interview (IDI) was conducted following the protocols for Social Distancing which is one of the mandates of AITF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. In this study, the virtual IDI was conducted with utmost care so that social distancing is followed and that at least 2 meters between persons was made. For some participants who missed the face-to-face social distancing efforts, the video-call via messenger, viber, zoom or google meet was used to gather the data or responses from the participants.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analysed. The researcher first

described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with full description of her own experience of

the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how individual were experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called "meaning units" or themes. She wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, she wrote a description of "how" the experience happened. This was called "structural description," and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the "essence" of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is that it's a flexible method which can be used both for explorative studies, where the researcher do not have a clear idea of what patterns is being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher know exactly what he or she is are interested in. No matter which type of study is being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis is that the researcher respects the data and try to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Document analysis. Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a systematic procedure to analyze documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other methods

of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data in order to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a larger qualitative or mixed methods study, where it is often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). When used in triangulation, documents can corroborate or refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources, which helps to guard against bias (Frey, Bruce B., 2018). Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. This is a way of assuring the validity of research through the use of a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. However, the purpose of triangulation is not necessarily to cross-validate data but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation - The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations and other factors such as time, day, season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirements as mentioned was the use of environmental triangulation best suit the environment of the research being conducted.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—

According to Braun and Clark (2006) methods of qualitative data analysis fall in two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) and methods which are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across a range of different theoretical and epistemological approaches and are therefore very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which through the theoretical freedom “provides flexible and useful research tool, which can potentially provide a rich and detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun and Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my own resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I use several nights to listen to the interviews to deepen my understanding on the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay-out and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved, and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step as data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note taking and summary while listening to the

recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used a number of different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts, the framework technique as developed by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003). This technique was useful to me in the process of coding, sorting and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedure included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with coded being the most basic segments of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub themes; Phase 5. I defined and named themes, making sure they give the reader immediate sense of what the theme is all about. Phase 6. I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes), used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments in relation to the research question.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—For trustworthiness of the study, I adhered to credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability of qualitative study. Credibility is how confident the qualitative researcher is in the truth of the research study’s findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do is essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues which ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue is “how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so.” Transferability is how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study’s findings are applicable to other contexts. In this case, “other contexts” can mean similar

situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using graphic organizer as strategy in teaching reading comprehension. The use of graphic organizer as a strategy in teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains analysis and creating. With this, the researcher is interested to know the students’ perspective of using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader is able to provide generalization of the study based on his own context and can able to address that core issue of “how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory.” Confirmability is the degree of neutrality in the research study’s findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants’ responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher.

This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability is based on the acknowledgement that research is never objective. Dependability is the extent that the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough

information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher can use inquiry audit in order to establish dependability which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis in order to ensure that the findings are consistent and could be repeated. In this component, the use of database is very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected must be properly kept for future use as references. Gasson (2004) states that dependability deals with the core issue that "the way in which a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the findings from the interviews with the subjects are discussed. During the interviews, their verbal comments were analyzed and summarized.

*3.1. Transition to post pandemic education—*The transition to post-pandemic education is a complex and multifaceted process that

will require significant effort and planning on the part of educators, administrators, and policymakers.

*3.1.1. Embedding online education beyond the pandemic—*Many schools and teachers have had to adapt quickly to new instructional models during the pandemic, such as hybrid and remote learning. In the transition back to in-person learning, schools need to continue to use these models in some capacity, while also adapting to new instructional approaches that better meet the needs of students. Pandemic or not, online education is now a part of the system. And while it does have its perks, a few disadvantaged ones do not have the resources to catch up to the digital age. This then leads to an imbalance in the equilibrium. While others are taking advantage in the availability of technology, those who are socio-economically challenged are left behind and fall back harder than the others. This poses a challenge to teachers as managers of

balance inside the classroom. Mitigating digital divide is one of the challenges in the post pandemic setting. Manfuso (2020) noted that distance education provides a well-considered learning ecosystem aimed at increased flexibility and better access to learning opportunities, through the careful design of unique courses that appropriately combine synchronous, asynchronous and independent study activities. In its turn, distance education, and in particular Internet-based distance education, refers to 'an institution-based, formal education where the learning group is separated, and where interactive telecommunications systems are used to connect learners, resources and instructors. This was the main instruction used during the pandemic when the students and teachers alike had to stay at home. But even as the transition back

to face to face setup has taken place, online learning still continues to be an option. Another consideration to take into account is that the emergency shift to online teaching overemphasized its remote qualities, arising from the need to avoid in-person interactions due to the pandemic restrictions. However, other aspects of technology-based teaching, which to a higher or lower degree were also present in traditional university practices, were underemphasised, probably because they were not as integrated in existing campus-based teaching as they could, or should, have been. Rapanta (2021) reported that one strong line of argument that emerged post-pandemic was that universities should be more relaxed about assessment, the channels used, assess less, and be more realistic about what capabilities can be assessed and how. He thinks that the discussions and controversies about assessment will enable some more serious and flexible thinking about assessment prac-

3.1.2. Learning Losses—The pandemic has had some irreversible damages especially to the educational sector. The learning loss is too big and impossible not to notice. Participants of this study narrated that the learning gap is evident among the students. It can be seen in the reading proficiency of the students and in other ways that indicate how the education has lagged behind due to the time taken away by the pandemic. In a study by Anggraeni (2023) in Java, Indonesia, The results of discussions between educators and parents/guardians of students about the learning development of learners during the pandemic concluded that cognitive, psychomotor, and affective abilities decreased dramatically. The educators really feel the learning loss when students begin to enter school to attend face-to-face meetings. Learners are not able to absorb the learning material delivered properly and optimally, the activeness of completing tasks is increasingly declining, and the level of adherence to instructions/in-

structions generally. Coincidentally, there has been a lot of good work coming out from some of the leading researchers and innovators in assessment and feedback – on areas like feedback literacy, peer assessment, assessment involving comparison with other students’ work, internal feedback, and so on that may be done in campus or online. The post-Covid times will be more open to more intelligent and diverse arrangements for both formative and summative assessment, and more open to including students in the discussion. He further asked, “Does the post-Covid challenge relate to how educational institutions become more digitalised, or to how pedagogically prepared and informed the curricula are?”. This echoes his previous research on the transition to e-learning, where it emerged that e-learning design was often a catalyst for a deeper instructional design reflection at an organisational level.

structions from educators and schools is also reduced. Not only has the impact on learning loss, this pandemic has also had a tremendous impact, including affecting the implementation of literacy activities in schools that have been running since 2018. Azevedo et al., (2021), warned that the actual impact that Covid-19 has had on student learning progress is just beginning to emerge. As the global education system continues to face pandemic-related disruption, a strong understanding of how Covid-19 school closures are impacting student learning progress can better equip educators, policymakers, and researchers going forward. Verhagen (2021) find that, overall, Grade 4–7 students in the Netherlands have encountered an average 0.08 SD learning loss in math, spelling, and reading. Tomasik, Helbling, and Moser (2020) found learning progress of primary-school students in Switzerland during in-person learning to be more than twice as high compared to the progress made during the eight-week school

closure. Orlov et al. (2020) determined that economics students at four USA universities were 0.19 SD behind. Kuhfeld, Tarasawa, Johnson, Ruzek, and Lewis (2020) found that Grade 3–8 students in the USA scored 5–10 percentile points below historic levels in math. Gore et al. (2021) found Year 3 students studying math in low ICSEA (Index of Community Socio-Educational Advantage) schools in Australia

3.1.3. Addressing inequity—The pandemic has highlighted and exacerbated existing inequities in education, particularly for students from low-income families and communities of color. Schools will need to prioritize efforts to address these inequities and ensure that all students have access to high-quality education. This is still the case even in the return of face to face instruction. Equity has always been present and continues to be an underlying issue that needs to be addressed. The United Nations (2020) reported that inequity is perhaps the most serious problem in education worldwide. It has multiple causes, and its consequences include differences in access to schooling, retention and, more importantly, learning. Globally, these differences correlate with the level of development of various countries and regions. In individual States, access to school is tied to, among other things, students’ overall well-being, their social origins and cultural backgrounds, the language their families speak, whether or not they work outside of the home and, in some countries, their sex. Although the world has made progress in both absolute and relative numbers of enrolled students, the differences between the richest and the poorest, as well as those living in rural and urban areas, have not diminished. These correlations do not occur naturally. They are the result of the lack of policies that consider equity in education as a principal vehicle for

to be two months behind the progress students made in 2019. Last, Schult, Mahler, Fauth, and Lindner (2021) find learning losses of 0.07 SD in reading comprehension, 0.09 in operations, and 0.03 in numbers for Grade 5 students in Germany. At the university level, in a single university, for 458 students in STEM faculties, learning outcomes actually improved.

achieving more just societies. The pandemic has exacerbated these differences mainly due to the fact that technology, which is the means of access to distance schooling, presents one more layer of inequality, among many others. They also highlighted that teachers are key agents for learning. Thus, their training is crucial. When insufficient priority is given to either initial or in-service teacher training, or to both, one can expect learning deficits. Teachers in poorer areas tend to have less training and to receive less in-service support. They added that education is a basic human right. More than that, it is an enabling right in the sense that, when respected, allows for the fulfillment of other human rights. Education has proven to affect general well-being, productivity, social capital, responsible citizenship, and sustainable behavior. Its equitable distribution allows for the creation of permeable societies and equity. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development includes Sustainable Development Goal 4, which aims to ensure “inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all”. One hundred eighty-four countries are committed to achieving this goal over the next decade.⁵ The process of walking this road together has begun and requires impetus to continue, especially now that we must face the devastating consequences of a long-lasting pandemic. Further progress is crucial for humanity.

Fig. 3. The key issues teachers experienced in the transition to post pandemic education

3.2. *The coping mechanisms of teachers on issues during the transition to post pandemic education—*

Teachers need to cope with the struggles and adjustments brought by the transition to post pandemic education. Having developed their coping mechanisms to address these struggles allow them to continue being effective teachers despite the challenges. Several coping mechanisms were employed by the participants to cope with the challenges they encountered.

3.2.1. Building a Support Network— Teachers have noted the benefits from building a strong support network, both within and outside of their school community. Participants of the study mentioned connecting with other teachers, joining professional organizations and participating in peer support groups. Even the simple comforts of connecting and venting out with colleagues on shared struggles during the return of face-to-face instruction have been proven to be an effective coping mechanism. The National Council for Mental Wellbeing (2020) published that having a social support system can have a positive impact on overall mental health, especially for women, older adults, patients, workers and students. Having a few people one trusts and can turn to can help manage everyday challenges, make difficult decisions, or even during a crisis situation. It can also combat social isolation and loneliness, both of which can put people at higher risk for physical and mental health issues including high blood pressure, a weakened immune system, anxiety, depression and more. They also added that everyone’s support system will look different. They can be anywhere from one to 10 people and include diverse people from different areas of ones life and that they take time to build. According to Matthews et al., (2019) associations among loneliness and neighborhood perception may also influence post pandemic mental health, yet may also see improved social cohesion, like studies following the SARS epidemic in 2003. Further, the shared experience of social distancing may be a protective factor toward more experiential types of loneliness, but individuals with preexisting traumatic experiences or unresolved grief may be particularly vulnerable. However, these findings do not take into account preexisting traumas or mental health concerns, nor do they address the financial, household, and family strain that may affect social support systems, connected-ness, and post-bio-disaster mental health. Similarly, Southwick (2015) noted the importance of social networks promoting resilience to stress and trauma. Using technology to socialize may also offer an important opportunity to meet the unique needs of children and adolescents. The negative effects of the COVID-19 pandemic reach beyond health and behavioral health care professionals. Raising awareness on the importance of self-care to reduce feelings of isolation and anxiety is paramount to promote well-being for everyone.

3.2.2. Staying Flexible and Adaptable— The post-pandemic education landscape is likely to be unpredictable and rapidly changing. Teachers need to stay flexible and adaptable, being willing to try new instructional models, technologies, and approaches as needed to meet the needs of their students. Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership (2016) stated that like other busy professionals, teachers’ engagement in professional learning is influenced by the demands of balancing family and work, and their resilience to the negative effects of this ongoing balancing act. Resilience in teachers can be understood as the capacity to “bounce back” in the face of adversity. Teachers’ flexibility is germane to their well-being and longevity in the professional workforce. Furthermore, teachers’ resilience affects their students’ learn-

ing and development. Adaptability in teachers is regarded as so important that it is the focus of selection for entry into teacher education programs and programs for teacher development. Zee Koomen's (2016) research into teachers' career adaptability is suggestive of its role in teachers' engagement and enterprising behavior at work. Career adaptability is positively associated with teachers' self-efficacy, which, in turn, influences teachers' professional optimism, and, moreover, their effectiveness as a teacher and intentions to stay or leave the profession. These findings lend support to the proposition that enhancing career adaptability may be another avenue to enhance resilience and reduce burnout.

3.2.3. Focus on Student Well-Being—The pandemic has taken a significant toll on the mental health and well-being of students. Participants of this study have voiced out the need to prioritize student well-being by incorporating social-emotional learning, mindfulness, and other strategies into their instructional approach. They also highlighted the importance of providing extra miles for students who have suffered the most learning loss during the pandemic. UNICEF (2021) discussed that school teachers and personnel are critical in supporting children's transition back to in-person classroom learning, particularly after extended periods of school closure. In addition to continuing to use the different skills teachers have been using to ensure their students' learning and emotional well-being while schools were closed, as teachers, it is essential to listen to students' concerns and demonstrate understanding as well as empathy. Teachers can support student mental health by being aware of signs of distress, connecting students with mental health resources, and providing a safe and supportive environment for students to discuss their feelings and concerns. Teachers can create a classroom environment that is supportive, positive,

The research shows that career adaptability, as positive psychological capital and a dimension of resilience, has a positive influence on engagement in professional learning. Adaptability is something teachers require on a regular basis and likely plays an important role in helping them to navigate the demands of their work. When teachers are more adaptable, they tended to report better well-being. Adapting may involve adjusting lesson pacing to better engage students, minimising frustration when a lesson is not going according to plan, or adapting one's approach to collaboration to work well with a new colleague.

and inclusive. This can involve setting clear expectations for behavior, celebrating student successes, and promoting a sense of community and belonging among students. Physical activity can also help students reduce stress and anxiety, improve mood, and boost cognitive function. Teachers can encourage physical activity by incorporating movement breaks into their lessons, promoting outdoor play and exercise, and providing opportunities for students to participate in sports or other physical activities. According to Leonard (2020), making time to explore and learn about students' experiences, particularly home-learning experiences, will be an important part of this transition – both for teaching and learning reasons. Students need time and space to readjust to school-based learning. For some, this transition will be filled with as much anxiety as the first day of school or the school year. Being prepared and catering for their potential needs should be of highest priorities. Teachers must provide multiple opportunities for students to explore their home-school experiences to support this transition. Class discussions during morning circle; while, writing, poetry, music, art, dance, drama, etc. would all provide authentic therapeutic opportunities.

Fig. 4. The coping mechanisms of the teachers on post pandemic education issues

3.3. *Educational management insights drawn from the experiences of teachers in the transition to post pandemic education*—The overall purpose of educational management is to effectively and efficiently create and maintain environments within educational institutions that promote, support, and sustain effective teaching and learning. This is especially ap-

plicable during the transition to post pandemic education. With all the changes, challenges and future hurdles that teachers experienced and will continue to experience, there are many educational management insights that can be drawn and applied moving forward. Some of the participants responses as pertains to their insights about their experiences were noted as follows.

3.3.1. *The Importance of Equity and Inclusion*—The pandemic has disproportionately impacted marginalized communities, highlighting the need for educational leaders to prioritize equity and inclusion in their management practices. Teachers wish to see support and actions taken that include addressing issues such as the digital divide, cultural competency, and access to resources and support. The Philippine Institute for Development studies (2022) discusses that inequality in the country may worsen if quality education remains inaccessible for low-income Filipinos. Socioeconomic status of families affects the quality of education received by children. This prevents educa-

tion in the country from being a “great equalizer” in society. Quality basic education, for one, can only be accessed by children belonging to middle-or high-income households. This makes them the only children able to avail themselves of quality education opportunities such as free education offered by State Universities and Colleges. The PIDS researchers lamented that the free tuition currently in effect will not solve the “inequitable access” to education that is being experienced by many low-income students. Affordable quality education is only one of many challenges faced by the sector, the PIDS researchers said. The challenges also include the pandemic which has forced mil-

lions of students to study remotely. Addressing inequity in education requires a systemic approach that includes policies and practices that promote access to high-quality education for all students. This includes equitable funding models, efforts to recruit and retain diverse teachers and school leaders, providing resources and support for marginalized students and their families, promoting inclusive and culturally responsive teaching practices, and addressing implicit bias and discrimination in school environments. Ultimately, creating more equitable education systems requires a commitment to social justice and a recognition of the value and dignity of every student.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the implications that were derived from the results and discussions in the previous chapter are presented. Future directions are also forwarded. The purpose of my study was to find out the experiences, coping mechanisms and insights of elementary teachers on the transition to post pandemic education. The participants were coming from Talomo, Davao City.

To achieve the research objectives, this study employed non-experimental qualitative - phenomenological approach using an interview guide. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines in which open ended questions for interview were applied to get authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored which was the transition to post pandemic education.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: The experiences of teachers on workload stress were mainly: embedding online education beyond the pandemic, learning loss and addressing inequity. The coping mechanisms to address the struggles were: building a support network, staying flexible and adaptable and focusing on students' well being. The educational management insight of the participants was mainly: Importance of equity and inclusion.

4.2. Implications—The Results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The experiences of teachers at Talomo District, Davao City on post pandemic transition were revealed in this part of the research. The following themes emerged after consolidating all the responses gathered from the participants of the study. The experiences of the teachers were focused on embedding online education beyond the pandemic. The pandemic has forced schools to adopt hybrid learning models that combine in-person and remote learning. Schools need to develop effective strategies to integrate these models to ensure equitable access to education and learning outcomes since the problem of connectivity remains to be an issue even post pandemic. Another theme to the experiences of teachers was learning loss. One of the most pressing challenges facing education in the post-pandemic world is addressing the significant learning loss that many students have experienced over the past years. This may require targeted interventions, such as tutoring, summer school, and additional support services, to help students catch up and get back on track. The third feedback was focused on addressing

Fig. 5. Educational management insights drawn from the experiences of teachers

inequity. The pandemic highlighted existing inequities in education, with marginalized communities bearing the brunt of the pandemic's impact. Teachers agree that there is a need to prioritize equity and ensure that all students have access to high-quality education, resources, and support. The coping mechanisms of teachers revealed these themes: The first one is building a support network. Teachers are seeking support from colleagues, administrators, and professional organizations. They collaborate with other teachers to share best practices, attend professional development opportunities, and join online communities to connect with peers. The second coping mechanism is staying flexible and adaptable. Teachers should be flexible and adaptable to changes in the education landscape. They can adjust their teaching methods and lesson plans to meet student needs and incorporate feedback from students and colleagues. The last coping mechanism is supporting students' wellbeing. Supporting student well-being will be a critical priority for teachers in the post-pandemic education landscape. By fostering a positive classroom environment, incorporating

social-emotional learning, encouraging physical activity, providing mental health support, and addressing trauma, teachers can help students thrive academically and emotionally.

The experiences of the teachers on the return of face to face instruction generally brought out one insight: the importance of equity and inclusion. Inequity and inclusion in education are important because they ensure that every student has an equal opportunity to learn, grow, and succeed. When educational opportunities are equitable, students are provided with the resources and support they need to achieve their full potential, regardless of their background, socioeconomic status, or identity. Both equity and inclusion are critical for promoting academic achievement, social-emotional development, and overall well-being for all students. When students feel supported and included in their education, they are more likely to feel motivated, engaged, and successful. Furthermore, promoting equity and inclusion in education helps to reduce achievement gaps and disparities, leading to more equitable outcomes and opportunities for all students.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. For the principals or school heads to be more receptive of the current situation and the struggles of the teachers. The school heads may involve creating a welcoming and supportive learning environment that values the wellbeing

of both teachers and students as they transition back to face to face classes. The teachers may continuously adapt to the demands of the job, both positive and negative. The teachers may practice adaptability and flexibility to face the challenges of the transition head on. For the future researchers, they may conduct the same study in a different location. Other factors may also be explored to open good avenues for the learner

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